

Importance of Jaina Inscriptions and Images from Kankali-Tila, Mathura

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Abstract

The historical site of Mathura stands as a testament to the harmonious coexistence of Brahmanism, Buddhism, and Jainism during the Kushana period. This paper emphasizes the need to construct a comprehensive history of Mathura by integrating inscriptions and art materials. Focusing on Kankali-Tila, Mathura, during the Kushana period, the study delves into Jaina inscriptions, Jaina images, and iconography to unravel their significance. The paper underscores Mathura's pivotal role in the visual expression of Jaina art, evident in the earliest Jina image found in Lohanipura (Patna, Bihar, 3rd century BCE). Jina images, Pratimasarvatobhadrika (Jina Caumukhi), Sarasvati representations, Ayagapatas, and narrative depictions from the lives of Tirthankaras further attest to the development of Jaina art and iconography during the Kushana period.

Key Words: Jaina inscriptions, images, Kankali-Tila, Mathura

Mathura was one of the earliest historical sites yielding art and inscriptions speaking of the harmonious relationship of Brahmanism, Buddhism and Jainism during Kushana period. It is very much required that history of Mathura should be written on the basis of inscriptions and art materials both and that too with holistic and composite perspective. The present paper will make a study of Jaina inscriptions, Jaina images and iconography at Kankali-Tila, Mathura during Kushana period to understand its importance.

After the Hathi Gumpha (Orissa) inscription of Kharavela, belonging to second-first century BCE, Jaina inscriptions from Kankali-Tila, Mathura are the earliest ones providing enormous information about Jaina imagesⁱ. Besides the Shunga period (c.150 BCE) *Ayagapata* having the figure of snake-hooded Parshvanatha with inscription, there are other inscriptions on *Ayagapatas*, images of Jinas (*Arhata*), Sarasvati and narrative slabs which also belong to Kushana period and are very important in the context of antiquity and popularity of Jainism in Kushana period. These inscriptions give the names of at least seven Tirthankaras namely: Rishabhanatha, Arishtanemi, Shantinatha, Sambhavanatha, Munisuvrata, Neminatha, Vardhamana (Mahavira).

Jaina art was first expressed in visual manifestation at Mathura, besides inscriptional evidence of Hathi Gumpha referring to 'Kalinga Jina' and earliest Jina image found from Lohanipura (Patna, Bihar, 3rd century BCE)ⁱⁱ. The Jina images and some other forms like- *Pratimasarvatobhadrika* (Jina *Caumukhi*), Sarasvati, *Ayagapata* and narratives from the lives of Rishabhanatha (dance of Nilanjana and consequent renunciation of Rishabhanatha) and transfer of embryo of Vardhamana (Mahavira, 24th Jina) were carved during the Kushana period (first-second century CE) only which served as the basis of subsequent development of Jaina art and iconography. Also Jaina *stūpa* was carved during pre-Kushana and Kushana period, archaeological evidence of which is found on Jaina *Ayagapatas*. Although intact *stupa* has not been found yet but their remains are in evidence.

The Jaina inscriptions of Kankali-Tila, Mathura found in abundance reveal that not only the Jaina *Acharyas* and *Sangha* but the entire society including *Nartaki* (dancer), *Veshya* (prostitute), *Pratarika* (sailor), *Lauhkarmaka* (iron-smith), *Suarnakara* (gold-smith), *Shreshthi* (trader), *Sarthavaha* (leader of traders) and even the ladies of foreign origin were contributing towards Jain Art.

The Jaina texts namely- **Sthananga-Sutra**, **Vasudevahindi**, **Nishithacurni**, **Harivansha-Purana**, **Adi-Purana**, **Uttara-Purana**, **Prajnapana-Sutra**, **Neminatha-Caritra**, **Vividhatirtha-Kalpa** frequently refer to the importance of Mathura in Jaina context. These texts give the names like- *Uttara Mathura*, *Mathura*, *Madhupuri*, *Madhupuhana*, *Mahura*, *Mathula* etc. According to **Adi-Purana**ⁱⁱⁱ (of Jinasena, ninth century CE), at the command of first Jina Rishabhanatha Indra created 52 *Karmabhumis*, Mathura was one of them. **Mahuraai Ahicchante Gatha** of **Nirvanabhakti** refers to Mathura as famous *Siddhakshetra* and *Tirthsthala* (place of pilgrimage). The **Nishithacurni** (*Uttaravihedhamma Cakkam Muthuraai Thumi*) refers to Mathura and *Devanirmitastupa* in Mathura. The **Yashastilaka Champu** of Somadeva (959 CE) also refers to Mathura and *Devanirmita-stupa* of Mathura^{iv}. The most important reference is in the

Vividhatirtha-Kalpa of Jinaprabha Suri (early 14th century CE), which mentions that the goddess Kubera got constructed the bejewelled golden *stupa* dedicated to Suparshvanatha (***Mathurayam Mhalakshmi Nirmitih Shri Suparshva Stupah***). This *stupa* was reconstructed and enlarged during eighth century BCE and it was rededicated to Parshvanatha as mentioned in **Vividhatirtha-Kalpa** (p.11). The present remains and depictions of *stupa* on *ayagapatas* reveal that in Shunga-Kushana period (second century BCE to second century CE) Mathura was main centre of Jainism and Jaina art. In one of the Kushana Tirthankara images (pedestal inscription of 167 CE, State Museum, Lucknow, Acc. No. J. 20) it is mentioned that the image was installed in *Devanirmita stupa* (*stupa* constructed by god).

Mathura has yielded *stupa* made of bricks (***Voddo Stupa***), alongwith profuse amount of Jaina images and other antiquities, which are preserved mainly in State Museum, Lucknow and Government Museum, Mathura. The antiquities are found mainly from Kankali-Tila, so called because of the presence of Kankali-Devi temple^v. According to Luders, out of 159 antiquities procured from Kankali-Tila, 87 belong to Jaina art while 55 and 17 respectively to Buddhist and *Vaidik-Pauranic* (Brahmanical) art^{vi}.

Out of the Jaina antiquities (both inscribed and uninscribed) atleast four show depiction of *stupa*. Two examples of fragmentary architectural remains, now in State Museum, Lucknow (J. 335 and B. 207), show the *stupa* with double *medhi* along with the *shravak*, *shravika* worshippers. The two inscribed *ayagapatas* contain the complete *stupa* on it, showing the developed form of *stupa* architecture, which is somewhat elongated having *trimedhi*, *torana-dvara*, steps to reach in other *medhis*, *Shalabhanjika* and *Dharmacakra*. The *ayagapata* in State Museum, Lucknow (J. 255) was prepared by *shravika* Shivayasha, while the other *ayagapata* in Government Museum, Mathura (Acc. No. Q. 02) was prepared by another *shravika* Lonashobhika. Both the *ayagapatas* refer to their installation for the worship of *Arhat* (***Arhat Pujaye***). These examples reveal *stupa* worship on one hand and the special support of women to Jainism on the other.

The inscriptions further refer to the Simhadatta, the wife of *Gramika* (head of villagers) Jayanaga for the making of *ayagapata-dana*^{vii} and Shimamitra, the wife of Gotiputra for making of Jaina image^{viii}. Further, the names like *Akka*, *Ogha*, *Okharika* and *Ujhatika* are apparently of foreign origin^{ix}, which denote that the women of the foreign origin also contributed to Jaina art. The Jaina inscriptions show that the Jaina community of Mathura consisted mainly of the traders, businessmen and artisan. In the inscriptions besides “*shresthin* (traders), *sharthvah* (leader of traders) and *gandhik* (perfumer) mention of *shuvarnakara* (goldsmith), *vardhikin* (carpenter),

lauhakarmak (ironsmith) are also noteworthy. Apart from the above *navik* or *pratarik* (sailor), *veshya* (prostitute) and *nartaki* (dancer) are also important^x. So far as the professionals community is concerned maximum references to *lauhakarmak*^{xi}, *gram-pramukh*^{xii} (head of villagers), *gandhik*^{xiii} and *shresthin*^{xiv} are found.

The *ayagapatas* are identified on the basis of inscriptions thereon which mention words like ‘*ayagapatas*’ and ‘*puja-shilapata*’^{xv}. The inscriptions also suggest the purpose and importance of antiquities such as *ayagapatas* set for the cause of worship of the Jina ‘*Arhat Pujaye*’^{xvi}. The pedestal inscriptions of the Jinas gives the expressions like ‘*Namo Arhato Vardhmanasa*’ and ‘*Namo Arhato Mahavira*’, which help in the identification of the Jina Mahavira even in the absence of cognizances^{xvii}.

A number of pedestal inscriptions refer to “*Shiddha, Arhat, Vrishabho* and *Ushabho* (Rishabhath), *Arishtnemi* (Neminatha), *Nandyavarta* (Munishuvrat), *Shanti* (Shantinatha), *Parshva* (Parshvanatha), *Vardhamana* and *Mahavira*”, which allude to their specific identifications^{xviii}. It is interesting to find that in Kushana inscriptions of Mathura nowhere Jina or Tirthankara words are mentioned rather ‘*Arhat*’ (one of the earliest expressions for Jinas) is used as ‘*Namo Arhantanam*’. Most of the inscriptions begin with ‘*Namo Shidham*’ and mention of Jina Mahavira as ‘*Arhato Vardhamanasya*’ in maximum pedestal inscription^{xix}.

Interestingly a unique form of the Jina image introduced for the first time at Mathura during Kushana period was *Jina-caumukhi* (four-fold) images. The exact identification for such images could be possible through the pedestal inscription of such images found at Mathura. In such images four different Jinas standing in *Kayotsarga-mudra* (motionless posture) are shown, which are labelled in the pedestal inscription as “*Pratima-Sarvatobhadrika, Sarvatobhadra-Pratima*(images auspicious from all the four sides)and *Caturabimba*”^{xx}.

The inscriptions also mention the names of several *acharyas, sadhu-sadhvis* and *shravaka-shravikas*, who have contributed to the development and popularity of Jainism during the Kushana period. The names include *Nandika, Arya Manguhasti, Arya Vridhahasti, Arya Sandhi*^{xxi}. Their genealogy and association with particular clan (*Gaccha*) of Jaina organization of Kushana period are also mentioned. The significant contributions of Jaina *sadhvis* are also known through the mention of “*Vasula, Data, Akka, Nandi, Sadita, Gockshaka*” like Jaina *sadhvis*^{xxii}.

It is clear from these inscriptions that the Jaina *acharyas* and the organization of Jaina *sadhu* and *sadhvis* alongwith *shravaka-shravikas* were also contributing to the development of Jaina art

during Kushana period. For example the Sarasvati image of 132 CE from Mathura (now preserved in State Museum, Lucknow, Acc. No. J. 24)^{xxiii}, refers to the carving of the image of Sarasvati (“*Sarasvato*”, earliest in Indian tradition). It also speaks of its preparation under the direction *Acharya* Aryadeva and was installed by the *Lauhkarmaka* (ironsmith) Gowa in *Nrityashala* (“*Avatalorangantarana*”- dancing hall). It also specifies the purpose that it was installed for the welfare and happiness for all (*Sarvastva Nam hit Sukham*)^{xxiv}.

Through the inscriptions we can clearly conclude that the Jaina religious and art activities during Kushana period was based on the integrated cooperation and help of the entire society, which included Jaina religious organizations, traders and businessmen, public, sustaining the spirit of religious tolerance. Thus the study of Jaina pedestal and other inscriptions from Mathura particularly of Kushana period offers very important and interesting information about the Jaina religious organization of Mathura and contributions of Jaina *acharyas* and organization including *sadhu*, *sadhvis* and common man revealing Jainism was a mass religion.

The pedestal inscriptions on the Jaina *aygapatas*, Tirthankara and Sarasvati images from Mathura provide very important and interesting information in the context of antiquity, technical terms and names of Tirthankara, Sarasvati and few others like Aryavation Amohini-*pata*. These inscriptions ranging in date from Shunga period (first century BCE) to 11th century CE are mostly belong to Kushana period (first-second century CE; *Saka Samvat* 05=83 CE to *Saka Samvat* 93=171 CE). On the basis of our study of Jaina inscriptions following observations are drawn:-

1. *Stupa* worship was popular in Buddhism as well as in Jainism. The earliest evidence of *stupa* worship in Jainism comes from Mathura, which goes to the Shunga period (first century CE). However the pedestal inscription of *Saka Samvat* 79=157 CE on the broken image of *Arhat Nandyavrata* (identified as Muni suvrat) refers to ‘*Vodde Thupe Devanirmite*’, which suggests the antiquity of *stupa* making and its worship in Mathura. The evidence is supported also by 14th century CE Jaina text **Vividh Tirtha-Kalpa**, wherein mention of *stupa* of Suparshvanatha at Mathura is found (which was subsequently enlarged at the time of Parshvanatha – eighth century BCE) to suggest the antiquity.
2. Several terms and identifications are also found in Kushana inscriptions such as *Ayagapata*, *Puja-shilapata*, *Pratima sarvatobhadrika*, *Sarvatobhadra pratima* (inscriptions of 93 and 110 CE), *Caturbimba*. It is noteworthy that *Ayagapatas* and *Pratima sarvatobhadrika* images are important manifestations of Jaina Art. The

- inscriptions also give the purpose of carving of these, which was worship *Arhat*(*Arhat Pujaye*), in inscription of 97, 120, 171 CE). Inscriptions also refer that these were carved for the 'Welfare and Happiness for All' (*Sarvsatvanam Hitsukhayastu*, in inscription of 96, 130, 132 CE). The expression itself is suggestive of the universal concept of welfare and happiness of all, which likewise is also found in Buddhist inscriptions.
3. For the Jinas only '*Arhat*' is found in inscriptions. Several inscriptions give the names of the Jinas such as Rishabhanatha (*Vrisabhoh*, in inscription of 124 CE), Sambhvanatha, Neminatha (*Arishtanemisya*, in inscription of 96 CE), Munisuvrata (*Nandyavrat*, in inscription of 157 CE), Shantinatha (*Santi*, in inscription of 97 CE), Parshvanatha (*Parshvasya*), Mahavira (*Mahavirasya*, in inscription of 171 CE) and Vardhmana (*Vardhmanasya*, in inscriptions of 83, 100, 107, 113, 120, 128 CE). For the antiquity of images of different Tirthankaras, these Kushana inscriptions are the only and earliest sources.
 4. The principles of *Tyaga*, *Sadhna* and *Ahimsa* were the main reasons of special inclinations of women towards Jainism as evidenced from the inscriptions, which give the names of women of foreign origin.
 5. The mention of different occupational community of trade and commerce in Mathura Jaina inscriptions are also especially important from the stand point of their contributions to the development of Jaina organization and art. The amicable and harmonious relationship among different community such as *Shresthin* (trader), *Sarthvah* (leader of traders), *Gandhik* (perfumer), *Suvarnkar* (gold-smith), *Vardhikin* (carpenter), *Lauhkarmak* (iron-smith), *Gramik* (head of village), *Veshya*(prostitute), *Nartak* (male-dancer) contributed immensely.
 6. The inscriptions also provide the names of Jaina *Acharyas*, *Sadhvis*, *Gana* and *Gaccha*, which reveal the existence of well organized Jaina *Sangh* at Mathura.

See chart – for details of Jaina Inscriptions of Kankali-Tila, Mathura:-

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G. Buhler- "Jaina Inscription from Mathura(Kankali Tila)". Epigraphica Indica Vol -I, 1983								
Inscription No./Page No.	Object(Inscription find)	Name of Donor M/F	Date (+78 C.E.)	Arhat/ Nirgrantha/ Tirthankara Name	Words donation (Pratisthapita/Dana)	Inspired by Acharya Name (M/F)	Using Word Icon/Pillar/Slab/Pratima/Sarvatobhadra	Important Points
I/381-82	Four Faced Jina Image Pedestal	Kshudra(F) (Sresthi)	Kaniska year 5(= 83 C.E.)	Vardhamana	<i>Danam</i>	-----	Pratima	Sresthi's Wife
II/382-83	Four Faced Jina Image Pedestal	Kumara Mitra(F) (Sresthi)	Kaniska year 15(=93C.E.)	-----	<i>Danam</i>	Vasula(F)	Sarvatobhadrika	Sresthi's Wife
III/383-84	Four Faced Jina Image Pedestal	Wife of Suchila(F) (Srvavika)	Year 19(=97 C.E.)	Santinatha and Arhat	<i>Danam</i>	Baladina(M)	Pratima	Adoration to the Arhats, (<u>Namo Arattanam</u> <u>Srvvalokutt(Manam)</u>)
IV/384-85	Pedestal of Standing Jina	Mitra(F) (Iron smith's wife)	Year20 (=98C.E.)	-----	<i>Danam</i>	Simhaganin(F)	-----	For welfare and happiness of all beings

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VI/385	Pedestal	Bodhinandi (F) married (Gram Pramuka)	Year 29 King Shaka of Kushana Period (=107C.E.)	Vardhmanas	Pratisthapita	Dataganin(F)	Pratima	<u>Arhat Pujaye</u>
VII/385-6	Pedestal of seated Jina	Kumara Mitra (F) (Gandhiko)	Year 35(=113C.E.)	Vardhmanasya	Pratisthapita	Baladina (M)	Pratima	Polished(Sansit Manta)
VIII/386	Pedestal	Datta(F)	Year 46 period of Huvishka(=124C.E.)	Siddham/ Vrisabho (Adinatha)	Danam	Kharnna(M)	-----	May the divine(and) glorious Rishabhabe pleased .
IX/387	Pedestal of seated Jina	-----	Year 44 period of Huvishka (=122C.E.)	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
XI/387-88	Pedestal of Quadruple image	Simhadatta (F)(Wife and daughter of village headman)	Year 40(=118C.E.)	-----	Danam	Akaka(F)	Thambho (Pillar)	Donation of Pillar
XIV/389	Pedestal of Jina Image	Gulha(F) Married	-----	Usabha (Risabha)	Danam	Jyeshthahastin(M)	Pratima	Kutumbiniye Danam
XVI/389-90	Pedestal of seated Jina image	Sister of Vishnusena (F)	-----	Arhat Vadhmanasya	Danam	-----	Pratima	

XVII/390	Upper part of sculptural Toran	Balahastini (F)(Sraman Sravika)	-----	Ahntanam	Pratisthapita	-----	Toran	Together with her parents, mother and father-in-law)
XVIII/390	Stone slab	Nandibala (M)(Actors of Mathura)	-----	Sidhama	Pratisthapita	-----	Stone Slab	Stone slab was setup in the sacred place to the divine lord of snakes Dadhikar: <u>For the welfare and happiness of all beings.</u>
XX/391	Base of seated Jina	-----	Year 22 (=100C.E.)	Vardhmanasya	-----	-----	Pratima	-----
XXI/391-92	Seated Sarasvati Image	Gova(M) (Iron-Smith)	Year 54 (=132 C.E.)	Sarasvato (Sarasvati)	Pratisthapita	Aryadeva	Pratima	<u>Srvstha- nam Hita-sukham</u> (For the welfare of all beings) Avtalo Rangan(artan) {In the avtala my stage dancer}
XXVII/393	Base of seated Jina image	-----	-----	Vadhmanasya	Pratisthapita	-----	Pratima	-----
XXXIII/396	Stone slab	Sivamitra (F)(Soldier or chief in the Army)	-----	Arhat Vadhmanasya	Pratisthapita	-----	Ayagpato	A black serpent for the Pothayas and Sakas(<u>Pothayasakas Kalvakash</u>)

G. Buhler- "New Jaina Inscription from Mathura". Epigraphica Indica Vol -II, Calcutta, 1984

Inscription No./Page No.	Object(Inscription find)	Name of Donner M/F	Date (+78 C.E.)	Arhat/ Nirgrantha/ Tirthankara Name	Words donation (Pratisthapita/Dana)	Inspired by Acharya Name M/F	Using Word Icon/Pillar/ Slab/ Pratima/ Sarvatobhadra	Important Points
I/198-9	Ornamented slab	Utaradasaka (M) (Sravaka)	-----	-----	Danam	Magharakshita(M)	Pasado Toranam	Gift of ornamental arch or pillar for the temple
II/199	Slab	Amohinhi (F) (Sravika)	Year 42 (=120C.E.) in Sodash Period	Arhato Vardhmans	Pratisthapita	-----	-----	For the worship of the Arhat (<i>Arhat Pujaye</i>)
IV/199	Sculptured Toran	Dharmaghosha(F) (Sravika)	-----	-----	Danam	Jayasena (M)	Pasado (temple)	A gift to temple
V/200	Stone tablet	Sivayasa (F)(Wife of Dancer)	-----	Arhat	Caused (<i>Karito</i>)	-----	Ayagpato	Worship of the Arhats (<i>Arhat Pujaye</i>)
VII/200	Stone tablet	Wife of Lavada(Mathurak) (F)	-----	Arhat Mahaviras	Pratisthapita	-----	Ayagpato	Name of Mahavir with the Ayagapata
IX/201	Jina image	Idrapala (M)	-----	Arhat	Danam	-----	Pratima	Worship of the Arhats (<i>Arhat Pujaye</i>)
XIII/202	Quadruple image	Masigi (F)	Year 18 (=96 C.E.)	-----	Danam	-----	Sarvatobhadra	For the welfare of all beings (<i>Sarvavanam Sukhay Bhavatu</i>)

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XIV/203	Base of standing Jina	Mitasri (F)	Year 18 (=96 C.E.)	Aristanem- isya (Ari- stanemi)	Danam	-----	-----	-----
XVI/230p.	Quadruple standing image	Jitamitra (F) (Gandhik)	Year 32 (=110C.E.)	Arhanta	Danam	Arya Nandik	Pratima Sarvatobhadrika	-----
XVIII/203-04	Broken image	Gottika (M)(Iron-Smith)	Year 52 (=130 C.E.)	-----	Danam	Aryya Manguhasti	-----	Welfare and happiness of all creatures (<i>Sarvasvanam Hitsukeyastu</i>), Preacher Aryya-Divitathe convert of the Gani Aryya-Manguhasti.
XX/204	Base of standing Jina	Datta (F) (Sravika)	Year 79 (=157C.E.)	Arhto anandiarvs (Nandyav-rat)(Muni suvrata)	Danam	Arya Vridh- astin (M)	Pratima	Was setup at the Vodva stupa, built by Gods(<i>Vodde thupe devanirmite pera--</i>)
XXIII/205	Base of standing Jina	Daughter of the goldsmith Deva (F)	Year 93 (=171C.E.)	Arhato, Mah avirasya, Vardhamana	Pratisthapit a	Nandi (F)	Pratima	For the worship (of the Arhat)
XXVII/206	Base of squatted Jina	-----	-----	Bhagvato Usbhas (Bhagvan Rishabha)	-----	Sadita(F)	-----	Name of Rishabhanatha
XXIX/207	Base of squatted Jina	-----	-----	Arhato Parsvasya (Arhat Parshva)	-----	Goshka (F)	Pratima	Name of Parsvsnatha

XXX/207	Stone slab	Simhana- dika (Vanka)	-----	Arhatanam	Pratisthapit o	-----	Aayagpato	Worship of the Arhatas (<i>Arhanta Pujaye</i>)
XXXII/207	Stone slab	Achala (F)	-----	Arhatanam	Pratisthapit o	-----	Aayagpato	Worship of the Arhatas (<i>Arhanta Pujaye</i>)
XXXIII/208	Base of squatted Jina	Datta (F) (House wife)	-----	Vardhman	Danam	-----	Pratima	-----
XXXIV/208	Base of large slab	Jaya (F)	-----	Vardhman- asya	Pratisthapit o	AryaSandhi	Pratima	For the welfare and happiness of all creatures.
XXXVI/209	Base of broken image	Vijayasiri (F)	Year 50 (=128C.E.)	Vardhman- asya	Danam	Ghakaraba (F)	Pratima	Who fasted for a month and obeys the command of Aryya ghakaraba (F).
XXXVII/209-210	Base of large quadruple image	Sthira (F)	-----	-----	Danam	Aryya Jestyahastin a	Sabadobhadrika	welfare and happiness of all creatures

Notes

- ⁱ M. N. P. Tiwari, **Jaina Pratima-Vigyana**, Varanasi, 1981, p. 17.
- ⁱⁱ D. C. Sarkar, **Select Inscriptions**, Kolkata, 1942, Vol. 1, pp. 206-213; M.N. P. Tiwari, **Ibid**, p. 17.
- ⁱⁱⁱ **Adi-Purana** (of Jinasena), parv-16, verse-155
- ^{iv} K. K. Hindaki, **Yasastilaka and Indian Culture**, Sholapur, 1949, pp. 416-433.
- ^v V. A. Smith, **Jaina Stupa and other antiquities**, Allahabad, 1901, p.1; N. P. Joshi and S. K. Rastogi, “*Kankali Ki Purasampada*”, **Jana Nibandh Mala**, Rampur, 1977, part. 01, p. 82
- ^{vi} G. S. Ghai, “Mathura Jaina Inscriptions of Kushana Period”, **Exprectrum of Jaina Art and Architecture**, Eds. U. P. Shah and M. A. Dhaki, Ahmadabad, 1975, pp. 21-36; S. K. Rashtogi, “*Dharma Triveni Mathura, Jaina Sthaptya evam Abhilehiya Sashya*”, **Arhat-Vachan**, Indore, year-18, pt. 01, Jan.-March 2006, pp. 55-68.
- ^{vii} **Epigraphia Indica (Epi. Ind.)**, Kolkata, 1983, vol. (B) 1, pp. 387-388.
- ^{viii} **Ibid**, p. 396.
- ^{ix} **Ibid**, pp. 387-388, 389-390, 391-392
- ^x **Ibid**, vol. 01, Inscription No. (**ins.**) 1, 2, 7, 21, 29; Vol. 02, ins. 5, 16, 18, 39
- ^{xi} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 4, 21; vol. 02, ins. 18
- ^{xii} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 6, 9
- ^{xiii} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 7; vol. 02, ins. 16
- ^{xiv} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 1, 2
- ^{xv} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 18, 33, 35; vol. 02, ins. 5, 7, 30, 32
- ^{xvi} M. N. P. Tiwari, **ibid**, p. 47
- ^{xvii} **Epi. Ind.**, vol. 01, ins. 1, 4, 7, 16, 20, 27, 28; vol. 02, ins. 2, 7, 23, 33, 34, 37
- ^{xviii} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 3, 6, 8, 14, 16, 18, 33; vol. 02, ins. 2, 5, 7, 9, 16, 20, 23, 27, 29, 30, 32; M. N. P. Tiwari, **Ibid**, p. 49
- ^{xix} **Epi. Ind.**, vol. 01, ins. 1, 6, 7, 16, 20, 27, 28, 29, 33.
- ^{xx} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 2; vol. 02, ins. 13, 16, 37.
- ^{xxi} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 3, 8, 14, 21; vol. 02, ins. 1, 4, 16, 18, 20, 34.
- ^{xxii} **Ibid**, vol. 01, ins. 2, 6, 11; vol. 02, ins. 23, 27, 29.
- ^{xxiii} M. N. P. Tiwari, **Ibid**, p. 48.
- ^{xxiv} **Epi. Ind.**, vol. 01, ins. 21, pp. 391-392.